

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

Project ID: 101098422

DELIVERABLE 1.3

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DELIVERABLE 1.3 – QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN

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Table 1. Revision and approval table

Version	Date of revision	Reviewer's name	Reviewer's comments	Approved
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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) serves as a comprehensive document that outlines the systematic processes, procedures, and activities necessary to ensure that key results, milestones and deliverables meet the quality standards. By doing so STECCI will achieve the set objectives:

1. Condition assessment of stećci tombstones and the reference group of sacral stone monuments in order to determine the level of CC and anthropogenic impacts
2. In situ conservation of stećci in different climate types of Southeast Europe
3. Development of comprehensive economy-based Preservation Guidelines
4. Promotion of stećci and European cultural heritage by enhancing cultural tourism in conjunction with creative industries and social innovation
5. Educating young researchers and conservators and increasing citizens' scientific literacy

The primary purpose of this QAP is to establish a framework for managing and controlling quality throughout the entire project lifecycle. The QAP relies on the Project Management Plan (PMP) which defines the roles and responsibilities, frequency of meetings and communication channels since effective and clear communication between partners is fundamental to the overall success of the project.

The PMP also contains a section about Risk Management to prevent or minimize negative impacts on quality. Further on, the QAP is closely linked to the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan that provides all necessary templates and ensures that all required communication and dissemination from other WPs, as well as the utilization of STECCI project results, are coordinated.

The Ethics Advisory Board will oversee the critical tasks with identified ethics requirements and ensure compliance with ethical principles throughout the project duration as defined in the Deliverable 8.1 OEI Requirement No 1. This work of this Board will contribute to the overall quality of the project. The QAP, linked to the above listed plans and deliverables, thus establishes procedures for review of project's key outputs and continuous improvement.

2. THE ROLE OF THE QUALITY ADVISORY BOARD

Members of the Quality Advisory Board (QAB) board will assist in reviewing the project's development and progress as a whole, and wherever possible contribute to STECCI's success, integration, and continuation on an international scale.

The members of the board are invited to provide critical feedback, suggestions and advice with respect to the research and training activities and to establish links with important national networks in the scientific communities, communication networks, and countries in and beyond the consortium.

Until project month M05, the Project Manager held individual meetings with QAB members with the aim to present the project, the anticipated impacts and discuss most effective ways of collaboration that will ensure high quality project outputs. Table 2 presents the members of the QAB and their respective expertise.

Table 2. Members of the STECCI Quality Advisory Board

Name	Expertise	Affiliation
Simon Warrack	Conservation	Consultant at ICCROM and World Monuments Fund, IT
Véronique Vergès-Belmin	Heritage science	Ministry of Culture and Communication, Head of Department – FR
Marinos Ioannides	Digitisation	Director of UNESCO Chair on Digital Cultural Heritage at the Cyprus University of Technology, CY

The role of the QAB is to provide expert advice on WP3-6 and the members will be available to offer advice at key points through the project and opinions on important project reports. The QAB will control the quality of main deliverables, as presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Involvement QAB members in key deliverables

No	Deliverable Name	WP	Lead	QAB Member
D 1.3	Quality Assurance Plan	WP1	UNSA	Veronique Vergès-Belmin
D3.1	Condition assessment report	WP3	UAA	Veronique Vergès-Belmin
D3.3	Conservation report	WP3	UAA	Simon Warrack
D3.4	Preservation Guidelines	WP3	UAA	Simon Warrack
D 4.1	Education Game Development	WP4	HM	Marinos Ioannides
D 4.2	Methodologies for low-cost digitization	WP4	HM	Marinos Ioannides
D 5.3	Report on the Stecci Summer Academy and Workbook	WP5	ZSI	Veronique Vergès-Belmin
D 6.2	Report on the cost-benefit analysis of the protective activities of tombstones under the effects of different climate change scenarios	WP6	UDG	Simon Warrack

To ensure continuous involvement of the QAB in the project and a good overview of activities the WP leaders, the Project Manager (PM) and the Coordinator (COO) will have on-line meetings as foreseen by the Project Management Plan (Table 4). The QAB members will also be invited to certain workshops, where relevant, to have a better understanding and a closer link to the project activities and goals. The leaders of WP3-6 will formulate questions and discuss the general workflow on their tasks and potential challenges with QAB members, in the first project months of their respective WPs and/or tasks.

Table 4. Frequency of meetings with QAB members

Frequency	Meeting notification	Agenda
Virtual meetings biannually	30 calendar days ahead	15 calendar days ahead
Virtual steering committee meeting if invited for advice	5 calendar days ahead	3 calendar days ahead
Workshops where relevant	30 calendar days ahead	15 calendar days ahead

The COO and PM will oversee the activities of the QAB and ensure its linkage to WP leaders, their contribution to the key deliverables and their participation in the Steering Committee (SC) meetings when required.

3. QUALITY ASSURANCE PROTOCOL FOR STECCI TASK PERFORMANCE

3.1. DELIVERABLES AND MILESTONES (TYPE, DISSEMINATION LEVEL, LABELLING AND TEMPLATES)

The STECCI deliverables and milestones are classified into group A (scientific) and group B (management related, administrative, technical and DEC-related). Each of the two groups will have a different review and approval procedure.

According to the Grant Agreement, the STECCI milestones and deliverables will be in form of different type of documents with two dissemination levels, following the coding system below:

	Group A	Group B	Group
<i>Public / PU</i>	fully open (⚠ automatically posted online)		Dissemination
<i>Sensitive/ SEN</i>	limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement		level
<i>R</i>	Report		
<i>ETHICS</i>	Ethics requirement		
<i>DEC</i>	Websites, patent fillings, vidoes etc.		Type of
<i>OTHER</i>	Other		deliverable
<i>DEM</i>	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype		
<i>DMP</i>	Data management plan		

Labelling format and templates follow the rules established in the DEC plan.

- Documents: YYMMDD_STECCI_name of document (e.g. 20240103 STECCI DEC draft),
- Deliverables: Deliverable.No_STECCI_deliverable short name (e.g., Deliverable 7.1 STECCI DEC),
- Milestones: Milestone.No_STECCI_milestone short name (e.g., Milestone 1 STECCI KoM).

The templates for reports, deliverables and milestones are available on EMDESK, in the folder “Templates”: <https://stecci.emdesk.com/#!/documents/direct/f14850>.

The Participant Portal permits the upload of a single file for each deliverable. 52 MB is the maximum size. The author is requested to adhere to this restriction when working on a deliverable.

Once approved and submitted to the EC, the deliverables and milestones are to be stored in the EMDESK folders titled: ‘Deliverables’ and ‘Milestones’.

4. QUALITY ASSURANCE PROTOCOL FOR DELIVERABLES, MILESTONES AND REPORTS

4.1. TIMELINE OF THE REVIEW AND APPROVAL PROCESS

By following a structured review process, STECCI will enhance the quality of their deliverables, milestones and reports, reduce errors, and ensure that project goals are met efficiently. The quality assurance is based on a bottom-up approach, starting from the lead beneficiary and WP leader (Table 5) who will act as first filters to the Steering Committee that will cast their vote before the deliverable or milestone is submitted to the EC. The role of each filtering stage (Figure 1) is described below.

Figure 1. The filtering system in STECCI quality assurance

Lead beneficiary and WP leader – are coordinating the complete and proper production of the deliverable. They clearly outline the contents of the deliverable and appoint the lead author(s). The deliverables and milestones are to be written in the designated STECCI templates. The first complete version of the deliverable needs to be sent to the review beneficiaries. Based on the feedback, the lead author(s) make necessary revisions and if required iterate through additional meetings with reviewers until the deliverable meets the required standards by day 15 before submission to the European Commission (EC). The WP leader is responsible for making sure that deliverable meets the quality requirements for dissemination to the EC and that it is completed in due time (Table 5). The lead author(s) are responsible of the scientific and technical adequacy of the deliverable content to the project objectives, at all stages of the deliverable review and approval process.

Table 5. List of WP leaders

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8
Lead beneficiary	UNSA	UNSA	UAA	HM	ZSI	UDG	UNSPMF	UNSA
WP leader	Nusret Dreskovic	Nusret Dreskovic	Marija Milchin	Andrew Pace	Pamela Bartar	Sandra Tinaj	Snezana Radulovic	Saida Ibragic

Review beneficiaries – are chosen based on their expertise in the subject matter and their role in the project. They provide constructive feedback, highlight weaknesses and suggestions on how to improve the quality of the deliverable. They check for completeness, accuracy and compliance with project requirements. Review beneficiaries will fill out the revision and approval table and be open for on-line meetings with the lead beneficiaries, COO/PM for additional discussions until due corrections are made. The revision comments are made using the ‘track changes’ option and are inserted into Table 6 (revision and approval table) that is to be placed under the History of Changes, as its supplement. Each milestone will have at least one reviewer from the consortium. The same applies for deliverables, however interdisciplinary deliverables will be reviewed by multiple partners. Tasks that are implemented at different sites in the partner countries and that lead to a common deliverable will also have multiple reviewers. The reviewers are listed in section 4.3 and section 4.5. The COO will be informed of any external event or risk that could affect the deliverable and all parties concerned will be called to a meeting to discuss a contingency strategy. In such a situation, the circumstances and expectations concerning this deliverable will be communicated to the European Commission Officer.

Table 6. Revision and approval table

Version	Date of revision	Reviewer’s name	Reviewer’s comments	Approved
0.0	[dd/mm/yy]	[beneficiary, name]	[comments]	[beneficiary name] [dd/mm/yy]
0.1				
...				
1.0				

Quality Advisory Board – is involved in review of group A deliverables only. Members of the QAB will be invited to review the outline of the content and take an active review role once they receive the first draft of the deliverable (day 30 before submission to the EC). The QAB members will fill out the revision of deliverables from group A (Table 7).

Coordinator and Project Manager – will notify the lead beneficiary, and in case of group A deliverables - the review beneficiaries, about the upcoming deadline for the deliverable and approve its content in the initial phase. They will ensure that all identified issues during the review process have been addressed and that the deliverable aligns with project goals. If required, the COO and/or PM can check with the internal reviewers whether all critical points were addressed accordingly.

Steering Committee – the final version of the deliverable / milestone will be shared with the SC 10 days before the submission deadline to the EC. The SC members will read the deliverable / milestone and cast their vote by filling out the Google form created for that purpose.

Table 7. Timeline of the review and approval process

Group A deliverables and milestones	Group B deliverables and milestones
70 days before due date for submission to the EC	
The COO or PM notifies the lead beneficiary and the review beneficiaries responsible for the deliverable on the due date.	The COO or PM notifies the lead beneficiary responsible for the deliverable on the due date.
60 days before due date for submission to the EC	
The lead beneficiary assigns the main author(s) and sends an outline of the deliverable content to the COO, PM, and the QAB if applicable.	The lead beneficiary assigns the main author(s) and sends an outline of the deliverable content to the COO and PM.
55 days before due date for submission to the EC	
The COO and PM review the content and provide feedback.	The COO and PM review the content and provide feedback.

30 days before due date for submission to the EC

The lead beneficiary sends the first complete version of the deliverable for an internal review to other beneficiaries involved (sec. 4.3 and sec.4.5), COO, PM, and the QAB if applicable.

The lead beneficiary sends the deliverable for an internal review to the COO and PM.

20 days before due date for submission to the EC

The reviewers provide their suggestions and comments to improve the quality, accuracy, scientific and technical adequacy where/if necessary.

The lead beneficiary and the COO / PM discuss the deliverable in an online meeting to improve the quality, accuracy, scientific and technical adequacy where/if necessary.

15 days before due date for submission to the EC

The lead beneficiary modifies the deliverables respecting the reviewers' feedback (organises on-line meetings to discuss) and sends the improved version to the COO / PM. The COO verifies that the feedback was addressed in a satisfactory manner.

The lead beneficiary modifies the deliverables respecting the reviewers' feedback and sends the improved version to the COO and PM for a final check. The COO verifies that the feedback was addressed in a satisfactory manner.

10 days before due date for submission to the EC

The final version of the deliverable is shared with the SC members who need to cast their vote.

The final version of the deliverable is shared with the SC members who need to cast their vote.

0 days before due date for submission to the EC

The COO uploads the approved deliverable on the grant management portal and submits it to the EC.

The COO uploads the approved deliverable on the grant management portal and submits it to the EC.

The numbers of days indicated in the table refer to the number of calendar days before the delivery date to the EC. The 30 days until submission to the EC are always the first day of the preceding month for easier use of the rule. Exceptions are deadlines which would happen on January, 1st. These deadlines are shorter and replaced with December 30th. The implementation of submission deadlines for the review and approval process will start with M06.

* The QAB is involved in review of Group A deliverables only.

Figure 2. Review and approval process of Group A deliverables and milestones.

Figure 3. Review and approval process of Group B deliverables and milestones.

4.2 LIST OF STECCI DELIVERABLES

No	Deliverable Name	WP No	Lead	Type	Disseminat. level	Review Date	Due Date
D1.1	Project Management Plan*	WP1	UNSA	R	SEN	[01/10/23]	[31/10/23]
D 1.2	Data Management Plan	WP1	UNSA	DMP	SEN	[01/02/24]	[29/02/24]
D 1.3	Quality Assurance Plan	WP1	UNSA	R	PU	[01/12/24]	[29/02/24]
D 1.4	Project Management Plan - Update	WP1	UNSA	R	SEN	[01/08/26]	[31/08/26]
D 1.5	Data Management Plan – Update	WP1	UNSA	DMP	SEN	[01/08/26]	[31/08/26]
D 1.6	Project Management Plan – Final	WP1	UNSA	R	SEN	[01/08/27]	[31/08/27]
D 1.7	Data Management Plan – Final	WP1	UNSA	DMP	SEN	[01/08/27]	[31/08/27]
D2.1	Analysis report on recent climatic characteristics and climatic types for STECCI case study sites	WP2	UNSA	R	PU	[01/02/25]	[28/02/25]
D2.2	The spatial-temporal distribution data base and modelling of selected air pollution impact within the selected STECCI case study sites	WP2	UNSA	R	PU	[01/02/25]	[28/02/25]
D2.3	Interactive digital STECCI Climate Atlas	WP2	UNSA	OTHER	PU	[01/08/26]	[31/08/26]
D3.1	Condition assessment report	WP3	UAA	R	PU	[01/05/25]	[31/05/25]
D3.2	Glossary of decay and damage patterns on artefacts made of compact limestone	WP3	UAA	R	PU	[01/07/25]	[31/07/25]
D3.3	Conservation report	WP3	UAA	R	PU	[01/02/27]	[28/02/27]
D3.4	Preservation Guidelines	WP3	UAA	R	PU	[01/04/27]	[30/04/27]
D 4.1	Education Game Development	WP4	HM	DEM	PU	[01/08/26]	[31/08/26]
D 4.2	Methodologies for low-cost digitisation	WP4	HM	R	PU	[01/11/26]	[30/11/26]
D 5.1	Handbook for Stećci Labs	WP5	ZSI	R	PU	[01/04/24]	[31/04/24]
D 5.2	Report on the implementation of Stećci Labs	WP5	ZSI	R	PU	[01/05/25]	[31/05/25]
D 5.3	Report on the Stećci Summer Academy and Workbook**	WP5	ZSI	R	PU	[03/01/27]	[31/01/27]
D 5.4	Policy Brief for sustainable Stećci Tourism	WP5	UDG	R	PU	[01/13/27]	[31/03/27]

D 6.1	Valorisation and economic analysis for the stecci sustainable tourism**	WP6	UDG	R	PU	[03/01/26]	[31/01/26]
D 6.2	Report on the cost-benefit analysis of the protective activities of tombstones under the effects of different climate change scenarios	WP6	UDG	R	PU	[01/08/26]	[31/08/26]
D 7.1	Dissemination, Communications and Exploitation STECCI Plan*	WP7	UNSPMF	DEC	PU	[01/12/23]	[31/12/23]
D 7.2	STECCI website*	WP7	UNSPMF	DEC	PU	[01/12/23]	[31/12/23]
D 7.3	Project promo materials and media press releases	WP7	UNSPMF	DEC	PU	[01/03/24]	[31/03/24]
D 7.4	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan – Update	WP7	UNSPMF	DEC	PU	[01/08/26]	[31/08/26]
D 7.5	Policy Brief 1	WP7	UNSPMF	R	PU	[01/02/25]	[28/02/25]
D 7.6	STECCI internet Platform and the data repository export	WP7	UNSPMF	DEC	PU	[01/08/25]	[31/08/25]
D 7.7	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan – Final	WP7	UNSPMF	DEC	PU	[01/08/27]	[31/08/27]
D 8.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1*	WP8	UNSA	R	PU	[01/09/23]	[30/09/23]
D 8.2	OEI - Requirement No. 2	WP8	UNSA	ETHICS	SEN	[01/08/24]	[31/08/24]
D 8.3	OEI - Requirement No. 3	WP8	UNSA	ETHICS	SEN	[01/08/27]	[31/08/27]
D 8.4	OEI - Requirement No. 4	WP8	UNSA	ETHICS	SEN	[01/08/24]	[31/08/24]

* - deliverables submitted prior the establishment of the Quality Assurance Plan

** - regular deadline would be the first of January

4.3. PARTNER RESPONSIBILITIES IN REVIEW OF SCIENTIFIC DELIVERABLES

Partner	Deliverable to review
UNSA	D3.4 Preservation Guidelines D4.1 Education Game Development D5.3 Report on the Stećci Summer Academy and Workbook D6.1 Valorisation and economic analysis for the stećci sustainable tourism
UDG	D3.4 Preservation Guidelines D5.1 Handbook for Stećci Labs D5.3 Report on the Stećci Summer Academy and Workbook
UAA	D6.2 Report on the cost-benefit analysis of the protective activities of tombstones under the effects of different climate change scenarios
SPK	D3.1 Condition assessment report D4.2 Methodologies for low-cost digitization
ZSI	D4.1 Education Game Development D5.4 Policy Brief for sustainable Stećci Tourism
UMAS	D.3.2 Glossary of decay and damage patterns on artefacts made of compact limestone D.3.3 Conservation report D3.4 Preservation Guidelines D5.2 Report on the implementation of Stećci Labs D5.3 Report on the Stećci Summer Academy and Workbook
UNSPMF	D2.1 Analysis report on recent climatic characteristics and climatic types for STECCI case study sites D2.2. The spatial-temporal distribution data base and modelling of selected air pollution impact within the selected STECCI case study sites D2.3 Interactive digital STECCI Climate Atlas D3.4 Preservation Guidelines D6.1 Valorisation and economic analysis for the stećci sustainable tourism D6.2 Report on the cost-benefit analysis of the protective activities of tombstones under the effects of different climate change scenarios
IMT	D3.1 Condition assessment report

4.4 LIST OF STECCI MILESTONES

No.	Milestone Name	WP No	Lead	Means of Verification	Due Date	Review Date
M 1	Kick-off meeting*	WP1	UNSA	Report after the kick-off meeting posted on STECCI platform	30.09.23 (M01)	[01/09/23]
M 2	Completion of the condition assessment of the reference sites	WP3	UAA	Reports on the condition assessment of the single reference sites and D3.2	30.09.24 (M13)	[01/09/24]
M 3	On-site landscaping and archaeological work on stećci sites in B&H	WP3	UNSA	Report on completed landscaping and archaeological work and D3.3	30.06.24 (M10)	[01/06/24]
M 4	Remedial conservation works on the stećci sites in B&H concluded	WP3	UAA	D3.3	30.09.26 (M37)	[01/09/26]
M 5	On-site digital acquisitions	WP4	HM	Reports after the completed acquisitions	31.08.25 (M24)	[01/08/25]
M 6	Post Processing of digital acquisitions	WP4	HM	Acquired and post processed acquisitions will be published on the STECCI platform and made available on Sketchfab	31.08.26 (M36)	[01/08/26]
M 7	Kick-off workshop for Stećci Labs managers and local partners from the consortium transferring the description of methods for Stećci Labs	WP5	ZSI	D5.2	30.04.24 (M08)	[01/04/24]
M 8	Storytelling experiment with participants in the SLs to create content for the Stećci Educational Game	WP5	ZSI	D5.2 and D4.1.	31.03.25 (M19)	[01/03/25]

M 9	Template for data gathered from social labs for policy use	WP5	ZSI	D5.4	30.11.25 (M27)	[01/11/25]
M 10	Completed collection of economic inputs for the development of Preservation guidelines and Policy Brief for sustainable Stećci Tourism	WP6	UDG	D6.2 and D3.4	31.05.26 (M33)	[01/05/26]
M 11	Towards greener conservation treatments on stone monuments in rural/remote areas – afield experiment	WP3	UAA	D3.3	31.03.27 (M43)	[01/03/27]
M 12	STECCI Website - beta version*	WP7	UNSPMF	D7.2	31.10.23 (M02)	[01/10/23]
M 13	Scientific conferences	WP7	UNSPMF	Report after two successfully organised scientific conferences (in Vienna and Mdina) and published books of proceedings.	31.08.27 (M48)	[01/08/27]

*-milestones submitted prior the establishment of the Quality Assurance Plan

4.5 PARTNER RESPONSIBILITIES IN REVIEW OF SCIENTIFIC MILESTONES

Partner	Milestone to review
SPK	M2 Completion of the condition assessment of the reference sites
UAA	M4 Remedial conservation works on the stećci sites in B&H concluded
UNSPMF	M6 Post Processing of digital acquisitions
HM	M8 Storytelling experiment with participants in the SLs to create content for the Stećci Educational Game
UMAS	M11 Towards greener conservation treatments on stone monuments in rural/remote areas – a field experiment
UNSA	M13 Scientific conferences

4.6 STECCI TASK REPORTS

Task Leader and WP Leader – are coordinating the complete and proper production of the task's reports. The reports are to be written in the designated STECCI Report templates. The first Draft version of the report needs to be sent to COO for review and approval 21 days prior the task deadline. The WP leader is responsible for making sure that report meets the quality requirements and that it is completed in due time. The lead author(s) are responsible of the scientific and technical adequacy of the deliverable content to the project objectives, at all stages of the deliverable review and approval process.

The COO provide their suggestions and comments to improve the quality, accuracy, scientific and technical adequacy where/if necessary, in 7 days timeframe after the Draft report submission. The Task Leader is responsible for submit the final version of the report version in 14 days.

COO is responsible to inform SC, at the regular SC meetings, on each report progress and approval, and after that to upload the report on EMDESK related Document folder.

5. CONCLUSION

The QAP relies on the Project Management Plan (PMP), the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan, DMP (Data Management Plan) and the ethic OEI Requirement No 1. The QAP, which is linked to the plans and deliverables described previously, creates mechanisms for reviewing and continuously improving the project's primary outputs. This will be accomplished by continuously improving and updating through D 1.4 Project Management Plan - Update (M36) D 7.4 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan – Update (M36) and D 8.4 – OEI - Requirement No. 2 (M12) .

REFERENCES

1. STECCI Grant Agreement 101094822
2. STECCI Project management Plan <https://stecci.emdesk.com/#!/documents/all/WP1-Del>
3. STECCI Dissemination, communication, and exploitation Plan
<https://stecci.emdesk.com/#!/documents/all/WP7-Del>
4. STECCI OEI - Requirement No. 2
<https://stecci.emdesk.com/#!/documents/all/Deliverables%20-%20WP8>